

REVIEW ON LIPID NANOPARTICLES OF TAZAROTENE FOR TREATMENT OF PSORIASIS

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ABSTRACT

Psoriasis is a chronic autoimmune inflammatory skin disorder characterized by accelerated keratinocyte proliferation and dysregulated immune responses, leading to visible skin lesions such as erythematous plaques and scales. Normally, skin cells mature and shed over a month; however, in psoriasis this process occurs within 3–4 days, causing cellular accumulation on the skin surface. Globally, psoriasis affects approximately 2–3% of the population, with notable gender and age variations, including a higher prevalence among men in India. The disease presents in multiple forms, including plaque, inverse, guttate, pustular, and erythrodermic psoriasis, each differing in severity, distribution, and clinical features. Plaque psoriasis is the most common type, accounting for 80–90% of cases. Psoriasis is associated with significant complications such as psoriatic arthritis, cardiovascular disease, metabolic syndrome, psychological disorders, and increased cancer risk. Clinical manifestations commonly include thick scaly plaques,

dry and cracked skin, and nail abnormalities. Management involves topical agents such as corticosteroids, vitamin D analogs, retinoid, and other anti-inflammatory therapies. Pathologically, psoriasis is a T-cell-mediated disease involving keratinocytes, dendritic cells, neutrophils, and cytokines, particularly those associated with Th1 and Th17 pathways. Cytokines such as IL-17A and IL-17F play a crucial role in sustaining inflammation and

lesion development. Understanding the immunopathogenesis of psoriasis is essential for developing targeted therapies and improving disease management and patient outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Psoriasis, Autoimmune disease, Keratinocyte hyper proliferation, T-cell mediated inflammation, Plaque psoriasis, Th17 pathway, Interleukin-17, Psoriatic arthritis, Chronic inflammatory skin disease, Immunopathogenesis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis is a chronic autoimmune inflammatory skin disorder characterized by visible signs of inflammation such as raised plaques and scaling of the skin. These plaques may vary in appearance depending on skin type and tone. The condition develops due to an overactive immune system that accelerates the growth cycle of skin cells. In healthy individuals, skin cells grow and shed over the course of about one month. In psoriasis, this process occurs within three to four days, leading to the accumulation of immature skin cells on the surface of the skin and the formation of thickened lesions.

Psoriasis affects individuals of all ages and can range in severity from mild localized patches to extensive involvement of large body areas. Based on the extent of body surface involvement, the disease is classified as mild moderate or severe. Beyond its cutaneous manifestations, psoriasis is increasingly recognized as a systemic disease associated with significant physical and psychological burden. The condition can negatively impact quality of life and is often associated with comorbidities involving the musculoskeletal and metabolic systems.

Although psoriasis is not contagious, its chronic and relapsing nature requires long term management. Advances in understanding the immunological mechanisms underlying psoriasis have improved diagnostic approaches and therapeutic options. Early recognition and appropriate treatment are essential to control symptoms prevent complications and enhance overall patient wellbeing.^[1,4]

1.1 Psoriasis statistics

According to the National Psoriasis Foundation, 125 million people worldwide – 2-3 % of the total population have psoriasis. In India 67% of all psoriasis patients were men, compared to 33% of all patients who were women (a ratio of 2.03:1). Patients ranged in age from infancy to the eighth decade, with a mean age of 33.6 years. 4.4% of all psoriasis patients

were children. In comparison to men (30.9 years), women had a somewhat lower mean age of onset (27.6 years).^[4,5]

1.2 Types

There are several types of psoriasis. The severity and location of symptoms may vary depending on the type a person has.

1.2.1 Plaque psoriasis

Plaque psoriasis occurs in 80–90% of people with psoriasis. It presents as raised and inflamed lesions but may vary in appearance depending on a person's skin tone:

- On light skin tones: pink or red lesions with silver-white scales
 - On medium skin tones: coral-colored plaques with silver-white scales
 - On dark skin tones: purple or dark brown plaques with grey scales
- Plaque psoriasis lesions most often occur on the trunk, buttocks, scalp, and extremities. However, they may appear anywhere on the body.

Figure 1: Plaque psoriasis.^[4,5]

1.2.2 Inverse psoriasis

Inverse psoriasis is a type of psoriasis that develops in skin folds and commonly affects -

The armpits

The groin

The areas under the breasts

Other skin folds, such as those around the genitals and buttocks

Inverse psoriasis typically produces lesions without the scales that occur in plaque psoriasis.

The lesions might be smooth and shiny.

Figure 2: Inverse psoriasis.^[4]

1.2.3 Guttate psoriasis

Guttate psoriasis occurs in less than 30% of people with psoriasis. It is more common in children and adolescents than in adults.

This type of psoriasis causes small, individual spots on the skin. They are not usually as thick or crusty as the lesions in plaque psoriasis.

Guttate psoriasis may resolve without treatment and never return. However, it is possible for the condition to clear up and reappear later as patches of plaque psoriasis.

Figure 3: Guttate psoriasis.^[5]

1.2.4 Pustular psoriasis

Pustular psoriasis is a rare form of psoriasis that appears as white pustules, or blisters of pus, surrounded by inflamed skin. It can affect specific areas of the body, such as the hands and feet, or present more generally. It is not an infection, and it is not contagious.

Pustular Psoriasis [generalized] Serious and life-threatening, this rare type of psoriasis causes pus-filled bumps to develop on much of the skin. Also called von Zumbusch psoriasis a flare-up causes this sequence of events:

- Skin on most of the body suddenly turns dry, red, and tender.

- Within hours, pus-filled bumps cover most of the skin.
- Often within a day, the pus-filled bumps break open and pools of pus leak onto the skin.
- As the pus dries (usually within 24 to 48 hours), the skin dries out and peels (as shown in this picture).
- When the dried skin peels off, you see a smooth, glazed surface.
- In a few days or weeks, you may see a new crop of pus-filled bumps covering most of the skin, as the cycle repeats itself.

Figure 4: Pustular psoriasis.^[6]

1.2.5 Erythrodermic psoriasis

Erythrodermic Psoriasis is an uncommon, aggressive, inflammatory form of psoriasis.

Symptoms include a peeling rash across the entire surface of the body. The rash can itch or burn intensely and spread quickly. It requires immediate medical treatment. A person may have large areas of inflammation across the body that could cause severe itching, pain, and large-scale skin shedding.^[1]

Figure: 5 Erythrodermic psoriasis.^[5]

1.3 Complications

Psoriasis may develop into other health problems that could affect the bones, muscles, and metabolic system. About 1 in 3 people with psoriasis develop psoriatic arthritis (PsA) within 5–10 years of receiving a psoriasis diagnosis. However, arthritis is present before psoriasis in 13–17% of cases.

PsA is a lifelong autoimmune disease that commonly appears in people 30–50 years old. It may cause pain, stiffness, and inflammation in a person's joints and progressively damage them.

People with psoriasis may also be at a higher risk of developing:-

- Depression
- Anxiety
- Cardiovascular disease
- Metabolic syndrome
- IBD
- Obesity
- Some types of cancer, including lung cancer, lymphoma, and non-melanoma skin cancer.^[3]

1.4 Symptoms

Psoriasis symptoms vary from person to person, but some typical ones include:

- Patches of thick, red skin with silvery-white scales that itch or burn, typically on the elbows, knees, scalp, trunk, palms, and soles of the feet.
- Dry, cracked skin that itches or bleeds.
- Thick, ridged, pitted nails.^[6]

1.5 Medications

- Steroid creams
- Prescription topical cream roflumilast (Zoryve)
- Moisturizers for dry skin
- Salicylic acid
- Coal tar (a common treatment for scalp psoriasis available in lotions, creams, foams, shampoos, and bath solution)
- Vitamin D-based cream or ointment

- Retinoid creams
- Calcineurin inhibitors
- Anthralin
- Tazarotene.^[3]

1.6 Pathology of psoriasis

Keratinocytes multiply within 6 to 8 days, and psoriasis is thought to be a T-cell mediated illness. The keratinocytes do not migrate from the basal layer to the skin's surface as quickly. While in non-psoriatic patients the keratinocytes would mature and shed off every 35–40 days. In psoriatic patients the keratinocytes form within a week and travel to the epidermis, resulting in non-evident lesions instead of falling off. A thicker epidermis, keratinocyte angiogenesis, and hyperproliferation are the results of the pathogenesis, which is caused by the activation of circulating immunocytes such as neutrophils, macrophages, T-cells, dendritic cells, and other products released by these immunocytes.

The dysregulated immune response that causes the histological characteristics of psoriasis is mediated by keratinocytes, T-cells, dendritic cells, and effector cells of the adaptive and innate immune system. Reduced differentiation and excessive keratinocyte proliferation lead to skin thickness, acanthosis (retention of the nucleus in the stratum corneum), and papillomatosis (extension of the epidermis into the papillary dermis).

Psoriasis red lesions are generated by dilated blood vessels that are packed with leukocytes that have accumulated in both the epidermis and dermis. pDCs (plasmacytoid predendritic cells), CD4⁺ T-cells, Th1 and Th17, and myeloid DDCs are all found in the dermis. Neutrophils and CD8⁺ T-cells are seen in the epidermis.

Due to the abundance of activated CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ cells found in psoriatic skin, it was once thought that both types of lymphocytes had an equal role in the inflammation caused by psoriasis. In a later investigation, psoriatic patients Th cells were transplanted into mice, resulting in the development of psoriatic lesions on the mice's skin. Additionally, the psoriatic skin contained more Th1 cytokines than Th 2 cytokines, indicating that the condition is a Th1-based illness.

Th17 in Th cells are essential in the development of psoriasis. An essential Th17 cytokine called IL17A is crucial for the development of inflammation in psoriatic skin. In comparison

to healthy skin, psoriatic skin has more CD4+ cells that generate IL-17A. There are six cytokines in the IL-17 family, and the IL-17A and IL-17F are the two that are most crucial for treating psoriasis. The presence of more IL-17 mRNA in psoriatic lesions than non-psoriatic lesions supports their function in psoriasis.

These CD4+ cells generate interferon and IL-22, two molecules involved in psoriatic inflammations. The CD8+ cells are resident memory T cells that are present in normal skin, but the psoriatic epidermis has a very high concentration of these cells. The blockade of CD8+ cells can be considered an effective treatment for psoriasis. By neutralizing monoclonal antibody, the CD8+ cells can be blocked.^[2]

Figure- 6 Difference between normal skin and psoriatic skin.^[2]

Figure 7: Diagrammatic presentation of psoriasis showing some drug targets.^[2]

1.7 Topical treatment used in psoriasis.^[2]

Agent or Class	Commercial Product(s)	Strength (%)	Application Regimen	Adverse Effects
Emollients	Aquaderm (C & M Pharmacal), Cetaphil (Galderma), Curel (Bausch & Lomb), Keri Lotion (Westwood Squibb), Lubriderm Lotion (Warner Lambert), and others	NA	Three or fourtimes daily	Folliculitis, contact dermatitis
Salicylic acid Coal tar	Various gels and lotions Balnetar (Westwood Squibb), Denorex (Whitehall Robins), Estar (Westwood Squibb), Neutrogena T/Gel (Neutrogena), Polytar (Stiefel), Zetar (Dermik), and others (available as lotions and shampoos)	2–10 1–48.5	Two or threetimes daily At bedtime; allow to remain on until morning	Skin irritation, salicylism Staining potential, skin irritation, photosensitivity
Anthralin	Dritho Creme (Dermik)	0.1–1.0	At bedtime; allow to remain on until morning. Short-contact therapy can also be effective	Staining potential, skin irritation, inflammation
Calcipotriol	Dovonex cream and ointment (Westwood Squib)	0.005	Once or twicedaily; not morethan 100 g of vehicle base per Week. May usefor up to 8 week.	Skin irritation, hypercalcemia risk
Corticosteroids	Ultravate cream and ointment (Westwood Squibb) Temovate cream and ointment (Glaxo Wellcome)	0.05% 0.05%	Two to four times daily for maintenance. May use occlusive wrap at night	Local tissue atrophy, fine hair growth, hypopigmen-tation, contact dermatitis, adrenal suppression
Psoralen	Oxsoralen lotion (ICN)	1	Apply to area 20min before UVAb irradiation	Photosensitivity, exaggerated sunburn
Tazarotene	Tazorac gel (Allergan)	0.05 and 0.1	Once or twice daily for up to12 week	Pruritus, burning, erythema

2] Drug profile of tazarotene

Name of the drug: - Tazarotene (TAZORAC)^[7, 8, 9]

Structural Formula

IUPAC Name: - 6-[2-(4, 4- dimethylthiochroman-6-yl)-ethynyl] nicotinate).

Molecular Formula: - C₂₁H₂₁NO₂S

Molecular weight: 351.46

CAS No.: 118292-40-3

Category: Antipsoriatic

Appearance: Pale yellow solid

Melting point: Between 103 - 105°C

Dissociation constant: 1.23

Partition coefficient: 5.7

Solubility: Insoluble in water, Soluble in DMSO, ethanol

Storage: Store at +4°C

Dose & Dosage: Tazorac is 0.05% gel

Minimum Purity: >99%.

2.1] Mechanism of Action

A particular retinoid that binds to the RAR is tazarotene. Even when used topically, the TZR has shown to have significant therapeutic potential in the treatment of psoriasis. One of the TZR's active forms is tazarotenic acid. It is attracted to the three RARs, RAR- α , RAR- β , and RAR- γ . However, it has demonstrated an affinity for the RAR- β and RAR- γ receptors. Markers of inflammation, keratinocyte proliferation, and keratinocyte differentiation are all impacted by the TZR. By TZR, the side markers were down-regulated. TZR-induced gene-1 (TIG-1), TZR-induced gene-2 (TIG-2), and TZR-induced gene-3 (TIG-3) are among the genes that are affected. For the purpose of modulating its therapeutic effectiveness as an anti-proliferative in the treatment of psoriasis, TZR up-regulates these genes. Therefore, likely

that TZR directly influences these targets to impact gene expression. Likely that TZR directly influences these targets to impact gene expression.^[10]

2.2 Pharmacokinetics of TZR

Tazarotene On non-occluded psoriatic skin and occluded normal skin, respectively, after 10 hours of topical Tazarotene treatment, less than 1% and 6% of its dose were absorbed. There is a lower risk of systemic harm when applied topically. As a prodrug, tazarotene is converted to its active form, tazarotenic acid, as well as sulfoxides, sulfones, and other polar metabolites in the skin and plasma. The elimination half-life of tazarotene and its metabolites is typically 17 to 18 hours, although their excretion through the urine and feces occurs 3 days and 7 days after their dose, respectively.^[11]

Figure 8: Pharmacokinetics of TZR.^[11]

2.3 Adverse effect of Tazarotene

- Itching,
- Redness,
- Irritation,
- Burning/Stinging,
- Scaling,
- Dry Skin,
- Peeling, Or

- Pain At The Application Site, And
- Skin Sensitivity to Sunlight.

2.4 Contraindications

- During Pregnancy or Breastfeeding
- Individuals who have known hypersensitivity to any of its components.^[12]

2.5 Background of Tazarotene

Retinoids include naturally occurring vitamin A and its metabolites. Retinoids exert their influence by binding to specific nuclear receptors. There are synthetic retinoid analogs including tretinoin, isotretinoin, acitretin, and etretinate that are metabolized to active agents and bind to all three retinoic acid receptors (RAR). Tazarotene is a synthetic retinoid, the first topical receptor-selective retinoid, to be approved for plaque psoriasis.

RAR and retinoid X receptors (RXR) are examples of retinoid receptors. There are tissue-specific isoforms of RXRs and RARs. Three subgroups of RARs are recognized: RAR- α , - β , and - γ . RAR- contains four isoforms, while RAR- and RAR- each have two. Each of the three subgroups of RXRs has two isoforms. RXRs are split into three subgroups. RXRs (bexarotene interferes with RXRs) govern cellular death and have the ability to partner with a variety of other steroid hormone receptors, whereas RARs regulate cellular differentiation and proliferation.

Tazarotene does not bind to retinoid receptors, but is metabolized in the skin to tazarotene acid, which can bind to high-affinity receptors RAR- β and RAR- γ . Basal cell carcinoma (BCC), psoriasis, ichthyosis, and other conditions characterized by aberrant keratinocyte proliferation can be successfully treated with tazarotene.

In contrast to the surrounding healthy skin, Duvic *et al.* found that the expression of the retinoid-inducible tumor suppressor tazarotene-induced gene 3 (TIG-3) is downregulated in psoriasis, squamous, and BCCs. Topical tazarotene also increased TIG-3 expression and reduced keratinocyte proliferation in psoriasis, BCCs, and normal human keratinocyte Treatment of moderate to severe plaque psoriasis, acne, photoaging, and keratinizing diseases with topical tazarotene: effectiveness and safety.^[12]

2.6 Analytical methods of Tazarotene

Pharmaceutical analysis is simply the proper quantity of analysis of a pharmaceutical company's medication candidates. Pharmaceutical analysts in research and development play a significant role in methodologies created and transmitted to QC or another department in the pharmaceutical sector.

For the tested product to be accurate and exact, straightforward, specific, affordable, effective, and reproducible analytical methods are needed. There is no official pharmacopeial publication that contains the TZR monograph. TZR is offered in the market as a cream and a gel.

In pharmaceutical formulations, the medication has also undergone qualitative and quantitative analysis. Accordingly, a survey of the literature reveals that several analytical techniques and their validation have been documented. For the determination of TZR in topical formulations as foam, ointment, and gels, various analytical methods.

Based on a thorough review of the literature, this graph illustrates how spectrophotometry, chromatography, and hyphenated methods like LC-MS/MS can be used to estimate TZR in topical medicinal dose forms. The spectrophotometric approaches, such as zero order, derivative, and multivariate calibration methods, accounted for roughly 42% of the methods for TZR measurement, while chromatographic methods, such as HPLC, accounted for 36%.^[13,14,15,16,17]

3. Introduction to lipid Nanoparticles

Nano particulate systems represent a viable platform for pharmacological therapy, with the ability to increase performance and overcome limitations. Among the several nano-systems studied, lipid nanoparticles hold enormous potential in the field of medication delivery. Müller and Gasco initially invented and named solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) in the 1990s to minimize the use of organic solvents in the preparation of polymeric nanoparticles (Muller *et al.*, 2011). SLN became one of the most promising systems because it was more stable than previously created liposomes, hardened at body temperature, which controlled drug release, and was free of the harmful consequences associated with organic solvent involvement. SLNs are colloidal carriers with sizes ranging from 50 to 1000 nm and a lipid forming core. This technique provides for maximum trapping and regulated release of hydrophobic medicines. SLNs could be improved by integrating lipid liquid into the solid structure, resulting in NLCs

with higher loading capacity and more stable composition. Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) are drug-delivery systems with a core matrix comprising both solid and liquid lipids. NLCs have been proven to have some advantages over conventional carriers for drug therapy, including enhanced solubility, the capacity to improve storage stability, improved permeability and bioavailability, fewer side effects, prolonged half-life, and tissue-targeted administration. NLCs have gotten a lot of attention in recent years.^[14,15]

Figure 9: Solid Lipid nanoparticle.

At the close of the 1990s, NLCs were launched as the next generation of SLNs, intended to overcome any potential challenges that SLNs might face. In storage, 14–16 NLCs increase stability, capacity loading, and stop drug expulsion. Their separation from SLNs can be determined by the solid matrix's composition. Both liquid and solid lipids are present in the lipid phase of NLCs at both room temperature and ambient temperature.

The next generation of lipid nanoparticles, known as NLCs, are modified SLNs that have both liquid (oil) and solid (fat) lipids in their lipid phase at room temperature. Since NLCs provide a combination of liquid and solid phases (oil) in a formless matrix, they are modified generations of SLNs that enhance stability and capacity loading.

Because of their irregular crystal structure, NLCs offer a better capacity for drug loading and can prevent drug expulsion by preventing lipid crystallization during the manufacturing and storage phases. The formulation of NLCs contains liquid lipids, which reduce the ejection of loaded medication both before and after formulation. Comparing NLCs to SLNs, they can exhibit more controlled release profiles and enhance drug solubility in lipid matrices. Despite having a lower melting point than SLNs, NLCs are nonetheless solid at body temperature.

Their irregular crystalline characteristics and unstructured nature provide for greater area for drug breakdown and payload in the liquid portion of the NLCs.^[23,24]

Figure 10: Solid Lipid and Liquid Lipid nanoparticles.

3.1 Classification of NLCs^[2]

- NLC Type I, also known as the imperfect type
- NLC Type II, also known as the multiple types
- NLC Type III, also known as the amorphous type.

3.1.1 TYPE I NLC

Because of their disordered matrix, these are sometimes referred to as imperfect crystal types. These flaws give drugs plenty of room to be integrated and have a high entrapment efficiency. Compared to solid lipids, less liquid lipid is used in this instance. When the oils and solid lipids are combined, they create an oil/water (o/w) Nano emulsion, which cools to room temperature and produces lipid particles.

3.1.2 TYPE II NLC

Compared to solid lipids, type II NLCs require higher quantities of oils. The formation of a miscibility gap between the two lipids (solid lipid and oil) is caused by a high oil concentration. Phase separation happens when these lipids cool down because tiny, oily nano-compartments form and are encircled by the solid lipid matrix. The controlled release of the medication from the matrix is made easier by type II NLCs.

3.1.3 TYPE III NLC

The Centre matrix of type III NLCs is amorphous but solid. The solid lipids and oils are combined so that the middle layer stays amorphous.^[25]

3.2 The composition of lipid nanocarriers with nanostructure

Particle size, drug release profile, and drug entrapment efficiency are all regulated by composition and procedure parameters. To get the intended results, the researchers have deftly taken use of composition and process parameters. For example, Muchow *et al.* reported that due to the greater mucoadhesion capability of small-sized NLC in the body, 200 nm NLCs demonstrated a higher area under curve values on oral administration in rats compared to 600 nm NLCs. The drug entrapment and loading capacity are also influenced by the degree of crystallization of the different lipids utilized in the formulation.

Excipient type	Example
Solid lipids ⁵	Beeswax, Carnauba wax, Stearic acid, Cetyl palmitate, Glycerol monostearate, Apifil®, Dynasan 112, 114, 116 and 118, Precifac ATO, Glycerol behenate, Hydroxyoctacosanyl hydroxystearate, Glycerol palmitostearate, Tristearin, Cholesterol, Palmitic acid, Hydrogenated palm oil, Imwitor®900 P, Geleol®
Liquid lipids	Decyl Oleate, Miglyol® 812, Transcutol® HP, LabrafilLipofile® WL 1349, Labrafac® PG, Castor oil, Oleic acid, Davana oil, Palm oil, Olive oil, Isodecyl oleate, Paraffin oil, Propylene glycol dicaprylocaprate, Linoleic acid, Decanoic acid, Argan oil, Coconut oil, 2-octyl dodecanol
Hydrophilic emulsifier	Poloxamer 188 and 407, Tween 20, 40 and 80, Polyvinyl alcohol, Sodium deoxycholate, Sodium glycocholate, Sodium oleate, Polyglycerol methyl glucose distearate
Lipophilic emulsifiers	Myverol® 18-04 K, Span 20, 40 and 60

3.3 APPLICATIONS OF NLC

3.3.1 Oral Administration

Higher drug loading capacity (LC) and entrapment efficiency (EE)

NLCs, which employ a mixture of solid lipid and liquid lipid in their formulations, overcome the drawbacks of SLNs by providing extensive drug loading, a superior release profile, and stability, as was previously indicated.

Numerous studies that compared SLNs with NLCs found that the latter were the superior carrier. For instance, it was determined that despite equal lipid occupation, drug EE in NLCs (95.3%) was higher than in SLNs (87.3%) in the research of ketoconazole inclusion in various formulations of SLNs and NLCs.

Control for drug release pattern

NLCs conduct a biphasic release pattern in the release profile, initially bursting and then maintaining constant. The liquid lipid located in the outermost layers of the NLCs creates drug- enriched packing, which causes matrix degradation by lipolysis or burst drug release initially by diffusion process. Drugs that consistently release core lipids follow this. By adjusting the ratio of the solid to liquid lipid composition, this property can be used to create NLCs with the desired release patterns. Due to their higher surface area and faster release than SLNs, NLCs also have the advantage of being smaller than SLNs, allowing for a full release in the GIT prior to gastric emptying.^[26]

Longer shelf-life storage

Given that the recrystallization process of solid lipid molecules to generate crystallinity after prolonged periods of storage results in considerable drug leakage, the suppression of recrystallization in the NLCs delivery system is an appealing concept. The NLCs model, on the other hand, is a matrix of solid and liquid lipids that prevents super saturation of the solid lipid composition and maintains the nano-sized drop of mixture consistent, or with small variation in polymorphism, allowing the system to contain the drug for a longer period of time.

Preventing pH and enzyme degradation

When it comes to oral administration of bioactive, such as peptides and vitamins, which are sensitive to breakdown by proteases and gastric acid, the extremely acidic fluid in the stomach and the presence of enzymes in the small intestine are often some of the constraints. The purpose of NLCs is to securely distribute these bio actives through the stomach before they reach the duodenum and jejunum. LBNs were stable in a wide variety of gastrointestinal pH ranges, from 1.2-8, were retained in the gastrointestinal system of mice for up to 8 hours and penetrated into the base of intestinal villi and colon. In a simulated gastrointestinal fluid test, NLCs containing vitamin D3 via Tween 80 and stearic acid accounted for less than 4% of the total.

3.3.2 Ocular Administration

Because of the ease of administration and patient compliance, topical ocular administration is the most extensively acknowledged non-invasive route of drug administration for treating ocular infections., Nevertheless, reflex blinking, tear turnover, tear dilution, and nasolacrimal drainage are physiological and anatomical ocular obstacles that limit topical medicinal drug

distribution to intraocular locations. Novel nanotechnology-based medication delivery systems for enhancing penetration across these obstacles have received a lot of attention. Lipid nanocarriers are simple to make, biocompatible, non-irritant, and have been shown to improve ocular penetration of numerous active medicinal components' NLC have been created as second-generation lipid- based nanoparticles to overcome the disadvantages of solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) such as low entrapment efficiency (EE) and drug expulsion during storage.

3.3.3 Topical Administration

NLC are particularly appealing colloidal carrier systems for skin applications due to their varied favorable effects on skin in addition to colloidal carrier system features. Because they are based on non-irritant and non-toxic lipids, they are ideal for use on injured or inflamed skin.

Researchers have extensively reported on the topical application of NLC. In recent years, SLN and NLC have been explored for topical administration with active substances such as vitamin E, tocopherol acetate, retinol, ascorbic palmitate, clotrimazole, triptolide, podophyllotoxin, and a nonsteroidal antiandrogen RU 58841.

3.3.4 Cosmetic use

Many properties of SLN and NLC have been reported to be beneficial for dermal application of cosmetic and pharmaceutical products, such as occlusive properties, increased skin hydration, modified release, increased skin penetration associated with a targeting effect, and avoidance of systemic uptake. In 2005, the first two cosmetic products utilizing lipid nanoparticles hit the market. The first two world-wide finished products with NLC, Nano Repair Q 10 Cream and Nano Repair Q 10 Serum, were introduced to the market by the German company Dr. Rimpler GmbH (Wedemark near Hannover/Germany, www.rimpler.de). Market introduction took place at the cosmetic fair "Beauty" in Munich October 2005. The NLC particles contain a relatively high loading of coenzyme Q 10. The final concentrations of coenzyme Q 10 are 0.5% in the cream and 0.1% in the serum.^[28]

3.4 Methods of Preparation

There are numerous methods which are used in preparing SLNs and NLCs, which are explained in detail as following

3.4.1 High shear homogenization (HSH) and ultrasound (US)

Both high shear homogenization (HSH) and ultrasound (US) are widely used and user-friendly dispersing techniques that were initially employed to create solid lipid nanodispersions. In simple terms, big lipid particles are reduced into smaller ones by a fast-rotating metal blade. Despite the fact that the usual particle size ranges from 100 to 200 nm, the presence of microparticles frequently reduces the dispersion quality. If ultrasound is used, metal contamination must also be taken into considerations.

3.4.2 High Pressure homogenization (HPH)

The development of HPH as a reliable and efficient method for SLN preparation. A variety of manufacturers offer homogenizers in the commercial market at affordable costs. For years, HPH has been utilized to create nanoemulsions for parenteral nutrition. Scaling up typically provides no issues, in contrast to other strategies. High pressure homogenizers force a liquid through a small orifice (a few microns broad) under high pressure (100–2000 bar). With a very short distance, the fluid accelerates to a very high velocity (about 1000 km/h).

Cavitation forces and extremely high shear stresses cause the particles to break apart at submicron sizes. To create lipid Nano dispersions, even larger lipid contents (up to 40%) have been homogenized. For the homogenization process, there are two broad methods that can be used: hot and cold homogenization techniques (Table 1). In both cases, an initial stage involves the medication being dissolved or dispersed in the lipid melt in order to be incorporated into the bulk lipid.

Table 1: Schematic procedure of hot and cold homogenization techniques for SLN and NLC production.

3.4.3 Solvent emulsification / evaporation

Nanoparticle dispersions can be created by precipitating them in oil-water emulsions, as described by Sjostrom and Bergenstahl. The lipophilic substance is dissolved in an aqueous phase of an organic solvent that is water-immiscible (such as cyclohexane). As soon as the solvent evaporates, the lipid precipitates out into the aqueous media, creating a nanoparticle dispersion. Depending on the lecithin/co-surfactant combination, the mean particle size can range from 30 to 100 nm. Bile salts were used as co-surfactants to produce particles with average diameters as tiny as 30 nm. Melt emulsification of equal composition does not produce comparable tiny particle size distributions. The mean size of the particles is influenced by the amount of lipid present in the organic phase. Only small fat loading (5% w/w) associated with the organic solvent allowed for the production of extremely tiny particles. Due to the higher viscosity, the homogenization's efficiency decreases as the lipid concentration increases. The advantage of this procedure over cold homogenization described before is avoidance of any thermal stress and disadvantage is use of organic solvents.

3.4.4] Microemulsion based SLNs and NLC

Gasco and coworkers created microemulsion-based SLN and NLC as an alternative to HPH. Microemulsions are multicomponent fluids made up of water, oil, surfactant, and cosurfactant that are isotropic and thermodynamically stable. Hot microemulsions containing low melting lipids, an emulsifier, a cosurfactant, and water are dispersed to create SLNs and NLCs. The extra cold water is then stirred into this warm microemulsion while it is being dispersed (a usual ratio of 1:50). When water is added to the microemulsion, the lipid phase precipitates, generating tiny particles. In order to boost the particle concentration, the extra water is removed either using ultra filtering or through lyophilization. This process has an advantage over homogenization in that it is simple to reach submicron particle size without the need of energy. The content of the microemulsion, the gradient in temperature, and the pH of the medium largely determine the product quality. For instance, a high temperature gradient speeds up the crystallization of lipids, which inhibits aggregation. This method's requirement to remove extra water from the prepared dispersion is one of its drawbacks. It is a challenging task. The need for a high concentration of surfactant and cosurfactant, such as butanol, might cause regulatory issues.

3.4.5] Secondary production steps

A) Sterilization: Sterile formulations are necessary for parenteral delivery. Filtration, gamma-irradiation, and aseptic production. To achieve sterility, heating and steam sterilization are typically utilized. Dispersed system sterilization through filtration requires high pressure and is not appropriate to particles larger than 0.2 μm . The features of the formulation, including its physical and chemical stability and the kinetics of drug release, should not be altered by sterilization.

B) Lyophilization: Lyophilization is a promising way to increase chemical and physical SLN stability over extended periods of time. Transformation into a solid form will prevent Ostwald ripening and avoid hydrolysis reactions. Principle option for SLN inclusion into pellets, pills, or capsules are also provided by lyophilization. It is anticipated that lyophilizates' solid state will be more chemically and physically stable than watery lipid dispersions. However, two additional transformations are required between the formulations, which could provide further stability problems.

C) Spray drying

An alternate method to Lyophilization for producing a dry product from an aqueous SLN dispersion is spray drying. Despite being less expensive than Lyophilization, spray drying has not been widely employed for SLN formulation. By spray drying, Freitas created a redispersible powder that conforms to the standards for intravenous injections in terms of particle size and constituent choice.

3.5 Advantages and disadvantages of lipid nanoparticles are as following^[30,35,36]

3.5.1 Advantages

- Controlled and/or targeted drug release
- Improved stability of pharmaceuticals
- High and enhanced drug loading (compared to other carriers) •
- Feasibilities of carrying both lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs •
- Most lipids being biodegradable, LNPs have excellent biocompatibility.
- Water based technology (avoids organic solvents)
- Raw material which are to be required are same as that of emulsion.
- Easy to scale-up and sterilize
- More affordable (less expensive than polymeric/surfactant based carriers)
- Easier to validate and gain regulatory approval.

3.5.2 Limitations

- Limited drug loading capacity due to crystalline structure of solid lipid
- Drug expulsion during storage due to the formation of a perfect crystal
- Particle growth
- Unpredictable gelation tendency
- Unexpected dynamics of polymorphic transitions
- High water content of SLN dispersions (70-99.9%)
- Low capacity to load hydrophilic drugs due to partitioning effects during the production process.

3.6 Characterization of lipid nanoparticles

For the purpose of quality control, SLNs and NLCs must be adequately and correctly characterized. However, because of the colloidal nature of the particles and the complex nature of the delivery method, characterization of SLNs and NLCs is difficult. Particle size, zeta potential, degree of lipid modification (polymorphism), coexistence of additional

colloidal structures (micelles, liposomes, super-cooled melts, drug nanoparticles), and time scale of distribution processes are important factors that must be assessed for the SLNs/NLCs. drug substance. Drug release in vitro and surface morphology.

3.6.1] A) Measurement of particle size and zeta potential^[26]

The most used methods for determining particle size are photon correlation spectroscopy (PCS) and laser diffraction (I, D). PCS, often referred to as dynamic light scattering, examines the variations in scattered light intensity brought on by the movement of particles with sizes ranging from a few nanometers to around 3 microns. Therefore, PCS is a useful technique for describing nanoparticles. However, it is unable to identify larger microparticles. By using LD measurements, they can be observed. This method is based on Fraunhofer spectra, which show that the diffraction angle depends on particle radius. Compared to bigger particles, smaller particles exhibit more intense scattering at high angles. From the nanoscale to the lower millimeter range, LD can detect a wide variety of sizes. Zeta potential, which has a high value and is expected to cause deaggregation of particles in the absence of additional problematic elements like steric stabilizers or hydrophilic surface appendages, is a crucial product characteristic of SLN/NLC. Zeta meter is typically used to measure it. Zeta potential measurements enable predictions regarding the colloidal dispersion's storage stability.

3.6.2 B) NMR spectroscopy^[34,38]

The qualitative characteristics of nanoparticles can be accessed via NMR. Because of various chemical changes. NMR signals can be linked to specific molecules or parts of them. The physicochemical condition of the nanoparticle can be determined by changes in the chemical shift that are related to molecular mobility.

3.6.3 C) Electron microscopy^[39,40]

Both scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) provide a means of physically describing and directly observing nanoparticles, with the former technique being preferred for morphological analysis. TEM is an excellent approach for validating other techniques since it has a smaller size limit of detection.

3.6.4 D) Atomic force microscopy (AFM)^[34]

In this method, a sample is scanned through with a probe tip that is atomically fine to create a topological map based on the forces between the tip and the surface. The exact type of force used to drag the probe over the sample (contact mode) or let it to run over the sample slightly

above (noncontact mode) serves to differentiate between the sub methods. This method's capacity is to map a sample in accordance with the ultrahigh resolution it provides.

3.6.5 E) X- ray diffraction (XRD)^[41]

The long and short spacing's of the lipid lattice can be accessed using the XRD technique. It is employed to look at the lipid's status. The removal stage may result in change of the lipid structure due to solvent employed in sample preparation operations. The sensitivity issues and lengthy measurement durations of traditional X-ray sources are overcome by synchrotron radiation. However, the majority of researchers have restricted access to this material. Investigations into the structural characteristics of lipids using infrared and Raman spectroscopy are still ongoing.

3.6.6 F) Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)^[41]

DSC can be used to characterize the level of lipid crystallinity and the alteration of the lipid. These factors are closely related to medication incorporation and SLN/NLC release rates. By identifying the kind and species of crystallinity inside nanoparticles through the measurement of glass transition and melting point temperatures and their associated enthalpies, DSC, like XRD, can be used to assess the status of the lipid.

3.6.7 G) In vitro release studies

Numerous research groups have used vertical or flow through Franz diffusion cells and dialysis bag/tubes for the study of drug release from solid lipid nanoparticles faster release than the enriched core model is achieved by the solid solution matrix model and the drug-enriched shell model. Although the slow drug diffusion from the nanoparticle's core causes the controlled and sustained release, the burst release is caused by the drug being captured in the outer shell. The concentration of lipid, drug, and surfactant in the formulation as well as the temperature maintained during the formulation of lipid nanoparticles are some of the formulation parameters that have an impact on the drug release. Temperature and water loss act as triggers for initiating the release.^[27,37]

3.6.8 H) In vivo / Ex vivo Release studies

3.6.8.1 Ex vivo Release studies: Permeation studies of a particular drug-loaded lipid nanoparticle are part of this study .The donor chamber of a Franz diffusion cell that is membrane-lined is filled with the SLN dispersion. Cellophane membrane and animal skin or tissue are used for in vitro and ex vivo investigations, respectively. At appropriate intervals,

samples are removed from the receptor chamber, and the amount of drug penetrated is determined using an appropriate technique (UV spectrometry, HPLC, etc.)^[43,44]

3.6.8.2 In vivo Release studies

Various animal modelling methodologies created for a specific type of disease can be used to evaluate the medications' bioavailability in vivo. Male Wistar rats were used by Diwan et al. to test nitrendipine's efficacy in vivo. A stomach incision was used to pinpoint the duodenum, and the prepared SLNs formulation was then directly injected into the duodenum. At predetermined times, tail vein blood samples were taken. After using an appropriate sample preparation technique, plasma was separated and its drug content was evaluated by HPLC. The pharmacokinetic data analysis revealed that the produced SLNs formulation raised the bioavailability of nitrendipine by 3–4 times.^[45]

3.7 Factors influencing drug incorporation and stability of lipid nanoparticles

3.7.1 Lipid drug interaction

- The drug's solubility in lipid melt
- The drug melt's miscibility with lipid melt.

In particular, there is an inverse relationship between loading capacity and the drug's solubility in aqueous media. Drugs that are more soluble in water have lesser entrapment effectiveness. The drug's solubility is a crucial consideration when selecting the technique of manufacture. The drug must be adequately soluble in the lipid melt (i.e., greater than required, since it declines when the melt is cooled) in order to obtain high loading capacity. Sometimes solubilizers are employed to increase the drug's solubility in the lipid melt.^[25]

3.7.2 Polymorphism (lipid modifications)^[34]

Following crystallization, the metastable alpha form of triglyceride nanoparticles often transforms into the stable beta form by a polymorphism process. The assimilation of the medication is also affected by polymorphic forms. While the bulk lipid preferentially recrystallizes in modification and transferring into beta -form (the most stable form), lipid nanoparticles recrystallize least in alpha-form. More perfect lattice results from the creation of more stable forms. As imperfections become fewer, drug ejection is encouraged.

Thermodynamic characteristics of polymorphs, such as melting temperatures, X-ray diffraction patterns, and solubility, change usually.

The main polymorph forms in glycerides are the α , β' and β forms described by Hagemann -
 α : Hexagonal (H) subcell with a lattice spacing of 0.42 nm.

β : Orthorhombic perpendicular (O) subcell with wide lattice spacings of 0.42-0.43 and 0.37-0.40nm.

β : Wide 0.46 nm lattice spacing in a triclinic parallel (T) subcell

3.7.3 Gelation

The phenomenon of gelation deals with the conversion of a low-viscosity SLN dispersion into a viscous gel, which can happen suddenly and unexpectedly and is typically an irreversible process. The creation of platelets in this process results in an increase in particle surface, which prevents the surfactant molecules from covering the new surfaces, leading to particle aggregation.^[22]

3.7.4 Supercooled state

In a condition known as supercooled melts, lipid crystallization may not take place even though the sample is kept at a temperature below its melting point. It is a size-dependent crystallization process, meaning that it must first reach a certain number of crystallization nuclei to begin. However, it is less likely that a critical number of nuclei will emerge in this occurrence. In other words, when particle size decreases, there is a higher chance of supersede melt production.^[26,30]

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